
Development of Crop Yield Prediction Model Using Machine Learning Algorithms: A Review

H.M. Munasinghe ^a, E.G.T. Dasunika ^a, W.W.L. Subhodani ^a, M. Janotheepan ^a,
E.M.U.W.J.B. Ekanayake ^a and T.A.N.T. Perera ^b

^a*Department of Computer Science and Informatics, Faculty of Applied Sciences, Uva Wellassa University of Sri Lanka.*

^b*Department of Export Agriculture, Faculty of Animal Science and Export Agriculture, Uva Wellassa University of Sri Lanka.*

Abstract

Machine learning (ML) has been used in agricultural production as a decision support tool to get insights, monitor crops, and equip farmers with vital information on crop variety selection and field management throughout the crop growth cycle. Several approaches to machine learning have been used to help predict agricultural yields. This literature review was undertaken to investigate the various ML techniques for yield prediction and to design a hybrid approach for Crop Yield Prediction Using ML Algorithms. The study's keywords were "ML algorithms," "crop yield prediction," and "hybrid ML algorithms" and 748 pertinent publications were retrieved. Using inclusion and exclusion criteria, we selected 50 publications from three databases for further analysis. The methodology and attributes employed in these carefully selected studies were evaluated, and suggestions for further studies were proposed. According to our findings, the most commonly used variables are soil type, temperature, and rainfall, and the most frequently employed method in these models is Artificial Neural Networks (ANN). Furthermore, ML approaches such as Random Forest (RF), Naive Bayes (NB), and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), as well as RF-NB, KNN-NB, and ANN-RF as hybrid ML models, are used to improve ML algorithm prediction accuracy. Because most ML algorithms are tailored to a certain dataset or task, and because they perform best when combined, integrating multiple ML approaches can significantly enhance the final product. Hybrid techniques, in particular, are the most successful crop prediction method and may be widely used with ML technology.

Keywords: Artificial neural network, Crop prediction, Climate, Machine learning, Hybrid approach

***Corresponding Author:** *hnirasha14@gmail.com*

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